

A TALE OF TWO LANGUAGES: TRANSLATING IRISH AND UPPER SORBIAN IN THE 21ST CENTURY

CZU: 81`25=152.1=162.52

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6521026

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This study compares two minority languages – Irish and Upper Sorbian – from a translation-based perspective. Firstly, the historical and contemporary status for both languages is described, together with information on the current sociolinguistic situation. This is then complemented by an overview of current translation and interpreting provision for the two languages in the relevant contexts.

Keywords: *Irish, Upper Sorbian, translation, interpreting, minority languages, language policy, translation policy, Upper Lusatia, Ireland, Germany*

POVESTE DESPRE DOUĂ LIMBI: TRADUCEREA LIMBII IRLANDEZE ȘI LIMBII SORABE DE SUS ÎN SECOLUL AL XXI-LEA

Acest articol abordează două limbi minoritare – limba irlandeză și limba sorabă de sus – dintr-o perspectivă traductologică. În primul rând, este descris statutul istoric și contemporan al ambelor limbi, împreună cu informații privind situația lor socio-lingvistică. În continuare, este prezentată situația actuală privind traducere și interpretare ambelor limbi în contextele relevante.

Cuvinte-cheie: *limba irlandeză, limba sorabă de sus, traducere, interpretare, limbi minoritare, politică lingvistică, politică de traducere, Luzacia Superioară, Irlanda, Germania*

Introduction

The third and most recent edition of the UNESCO *Atlas of the World's Languages in Danger* [1] lists over two thousand endangered tongues, including Irish (*Gaeilge*) and – under a single entry for “Sorbian” – Upper Sorbian (*hornjoserbšćina*). Of the six degrees of linguistic vitality outlined in the *Atlas* [1, pp. 11-12], Irish and Upper Sorbian share the status of “definitely endangered”, which broadly means that transmission of these languages between different generations – grandparents, parents, and children – can no longer be guaranteed. Although at first there may appear to be few similarities between a Celtic language spoken on the north-western Atlantic coast of Europe, and a Slavic language spoken in Saxony (eastern Germany) near to the Polish and Czech borders, a closer look reveals several common features worthy of closer examination. A significant number of studies on various historical, cultural, educational, and linguistic aspects of each of these two minority languages has already been conducted (recent publications include, for example, [2-3]), but wider comparative work on Irish and Upper Sorbian remains relatively rare. Hence, building on the author's previous research which has explored the institutional linguistic and translation policies of various minority languages (for example, see [4-6]), this study aims to provide a preliminary overview of the status and relevant historical and contemporary milieu regarding Irish and Upper Sorbian from a translation and interpreting-based perspective. Accordingly, after a brief overview of the methodological framework utilised, a bipartite presentation of the findings will be made. In the first instance, the historical development of both Irish and Upper Sorbian will be outlined, complemented by information on the current sociolinguistic and sociocultural situation regarding the two languages. Subsequently, this will be supplemented by a comparative analysis of the current translation- and interpreting-related provision for Irish and Upper Sorbian with a focus on the institutional environments.

Methodological approach and research questions

The crucial role of translation for less-widely spoken languages has been well-attested over the last few years, as evidenced by a range of studies examining relevant translation policy and practices (see for example, [7-8] etc.). Aside from theoretical aspects, the impact of the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic has starkly accentuated the issues and challenges that language barriers can create [9], and thus the practical importance of translation for minority languages at this time of crisis (for example, see [10-11]). In acknowledging the role that the translation of minority languages can also play in other domains – such as the arts, literature, and culture – this study, mindful of limitations of time and space, focuses squarely on providing a comparative overview of relevant societal and institutional aspects relating directly to the Irish and Upper Sorbian contexts.

Accordingly, two research questions were proposed:

- i) What is the historical and contemporary status of Irish and Upper Sorbian?
- ii) What is the current translation and interpreting-related situation regarding Irish and Upper Sorbian?

The aforementioned limitations meant that a literature-based approach was selected as the chosen methodology, with the intention of supplementing the current basic overview with fieldwork at a subsequent future time. As a result, in a similar manner to the author's previous analysis of official language certifications for Irish and Upper Sorbian [12], information was obtained from scholarly sources such as academic books and articles, as well as from relevant institutional websites and online journalistic resources.

Findings and discussion

To explore the current status of Irish and Upper Sorbian, an overview of the relevant geographical, historical, and sociolinguistic information is required. As such, in terms of geography, Irish is spoken in the Republic of Ireland, where it is the country's first official language alongside English. In practical terms, however, given the overwhelming dominance of English, it is typically used for daily communication in special linguistic zones (*Gaeltachtaí*), which are generally situated in rural areas away from large urban settings. This mostly rural-based milieu is also largely shared by Upper Sorbian, which is spoken alongside German within the mainly rural historical region of Upper Lusatia in the German federal state of Saxony. Though both languages have long heritages stretching back to before medieval times and were formerly widely spoken across larger areas of territory, the vicissitudes of history – including war and subjugation by external parties – have meant that both Irish and Upper Sorbian have been subjected to marginalisation and dominance by larger linguistic, political, and cultural forces. In the case of Irish, this is embodied by the strong influence exerted by the English language, and by German in the case of Upper Sorbian (for more information, please see [13-14]).

In addition, there is some uncertainty regarding the precise number of speakers of both languages. As also noted elsewhere [15], in the case of Irish, the census of 2016 stated over 1.8 million speakers had knowledge of the language, but only just over 70,000 spoke the language each day [16]; a further census, postponed from 2021, is planned for spring 2022 [17]. Regarding Upper Sorbian, estimates of the number of speakers vary, but a recent informational travel article published by the BBC [18] noted that there are around 20,000 people who speak the language, a figure generally consistent with the numbers mooted in the relevant scholarly literature. As observed by Adler and Beyer [19, p. 230], more exact figures may be available in the near future,

as, for the first time in almost eight decades, the 2017 German census included a question on language.

Furthermore, given their marginalised status, both languages have undergone – or are in the process of – linguistic revitalisation. In Ireland, this commenced in the 1880s and accelerated after the country gained independence from the United Kingdom in the 20th century; with regard to Upper Sorbian, this process has quickened after the reunification of Germany in the 1990s, although, as noted elsewhere, during East German times the Sorbian languages and culture did enjoy a certain prestige [13-14]. As with any linguistic revitalisation efforts, education and training is crucial to promoting and promulgating the use of the two languages in the relevant contexts. Primary, secondary, and tertiary education is available in both languages, and has been the object of a significant body of research with both Irish (for example, see [20-22]) and Upper Sorbian (e.g. [3], [14], [23]). Principally through official signage, both languages are present in the relevant linguistic landscapes of the Republic of Ireland [24] and Upper Lusatia [25]). In addition, there is considerable media available in Irish, including newspapers, radio, and a full television channel, TG4 [26-27]. For Upper Sorbian, though the amount of media is smaller, newspapers, radio, and some television programming is also offered [14, p. 61].

A major difference between Irish and Upper Sorbian, however, relates to their wider status. Its position as a minority language notwithstanding, Irish has the status of first official language of the Republic of Ireland, as was mentioned previously. In addition, it is also one of the 24 official languages of the European Union (EU) and its institutions [28]. Although Irish has held this latter distinction since 2007, it was not until a decade-and-a-half later, on 1 January 2022, that its full implementation as an official and working language at the EU level was completed, an event that was welcomed by the President of Ireland as a “historic occasion” [29]. By way of contrast, Upper Sorbian does not currently enjoy supranational status, although – together with Lower Sorbian – it is recognised as one of Germany’s minority languages [19, p. 223]. As such, unlike Irish, its usage remains rather localised and thus it is extremely unlikely to be commonly utilised in debates and fora at the European level at present.

Turning to translation and interpreting, both have played a key role in the Irish context since medieval and early modern times (for an excellent panorama, please see [30]). As noted above, in official terms the Republic of Ireland is a bilingual nation, and though Irish attained the status of an official EU language in 2007, the delay in its full implementation at the supranational level was because of a corresponding derogation. As outlined elsewhere [31], subsequent efforts to recruit linguistic staff with the required skills were highlighted in the country’s domestic print media; indeed, the author’s research illustrated that as a result, this led to increased visibility of translators and interpreters in Ireland itself (see, for example [15], [32]). In terms of national language policy, the recent ratification of the Official Languages Amendment Act [33], which promotes the usage, access, and availability of relevant state materials in the Irish language, will doubtlessly also prove noteworthy for translation and interpreting provision at the domestic political level.

In terms of possibilities for translator and interpreter training, it is clear that relevant demand means that there are several courses offered with Irish. By way of example, the website of the professional body, the Irish Translators and Interpreters Association (ITIA) lists undergraduate and postgraduate courses relating to translation, interpreting, and applied languages at several tertiary institutions in the country [34-35]). In addition, two postgraduate courses at Dublin City University and one at University College Cork are members of the prestigious European Masters in Translation consortium [36], a pan-European quality marker of best practice in translator education, and future

conference interpreters with Irish are trained via the postgraduate course at NUI Galway, which cooperates with the EU institutions [37].

For Upper Sorbian however, translator and interpreter training possibilities are more limited. As observed in the author's previous publication [6], there is no university within Upper Lusatia itself, and tertiary-level degrees in Upper and Lower Sorbian are centred in the University of Leipzig (for an overview of the educational programmes there, please see [38]). However, as noted by the author [6, p. 10], a search of the course directories of the postgraduate translation and conference interpreting degrees at that time showed that Upper Sorbian did not appear to be offered within the language combinations listed; however, translation options did seem to feature within the syllabi of the degrees in Sorbian studies. As was also highlighted in the author's previous study [6, p. 10], translation and interpreting do seem to be becoming more prominent in the Upper Sorbian context – as exemplified by the delivery of relevant interpreting equipment and also by the creation of a specific public institution responsible for language-related issues – including translation and interpreting – in Upper Lusatia.

Finally, as with many other languages across the world, artificial intelligence as it relates to machine translation and post-editing will certainly play an increasingly important role in the translation of Irish and Upper Sorbian both in the contemporary environment and also as the century progresses. Irish already features not only in open-access machine translation software like Google Translate and Microsoft's Bing Translator, but is also one of the languages available on the European Commission's eTranslation neural translation tool [39]. For Upper Sorbian, machine translation based on the Upper Sorbian-German language pair has been offered through the Sotra portal [40]. Most recently, as of February 2022, Upper Sorbian is now also available through Microsoft Bing Translator [41-42]. Indeed, this ensures that, together with the existing machine translation software available for Irish, both languages can have a global reach and are thus accessible to all.

Concluding remarks and possibilities for subsequent research

As noted at the outset of this contribution, Irish and Upper Sorbian may appear to have few similarities on first appearances. However, through exploration of the relevant geographical, historical, and sociolinguistic context for both languages, a number of surprising similarities have been uncovered. In the first instance, both languages have had long histories but have become marginalised through being overshadowed by the dominance of a bigger linguistic, cultural, and political neighbour. Nonetheless, school and university study programmes are available in both languages, and both Irish and Upper Sorbian are currently undergoing revitalisation processes, as demonstrated by the promotion and promulgation of both languages in education. Both tongues also have relevant mass media such as newspapers, radio, and television available, and both languages are visible on official bilingual signage.

Differences emerge, however, with regard to the official status of both languages. Upper Sorbian, whilst a recognised minority language, is limited largely to the territory of Upper Lusatia, whereas Irish, through its status as one of the EU's official languages, has become visible at the European level, with a resultant fillip to the visibility of the language in the Republic of Ireland itself. This divergence in the status of the two languages is also illustrated in the availability of translator and interpreter training options – for example, there are several undergraduate and postgraduate opportunities for Irish speakers; whereas provision for Upper Sorbian is more limited in this regard at present, but this may certainly change in the future. With regard to machine

translation, the integration of both languages into widely-used automatic translation software is an encouraging sign, thereby providing a template for the promotion and spread of similar such tools for other minority languages in the European context and beyond.

The brief nature of this preliminary overview means that it has not been possible to delve into the numerous points raised in significant depth. However, building on the information provided here, it is clear that there are a number of aspects that require further investigation, including from historical, sociolinguistic, and educational perspectives. Notably, it would be of interest to explore some of these relevant points using the collection of empirical data from a variety of sources, thus going beyond the limitations inherent in a purely literature-based analysis. Accordingly, it is hoped that in the future comparative – and ideally interdisciplinary – work between the Irish and Upper Sorbian contexts will be conducted, with the aim of bringing new research insights to this important and valuable area of study.

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